

Topology-Informed Jet Tagging using Persistent Homology

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Abstract

This report presents a compact overview of a topology informed approach to classify particle jets using persistent homology. Using the publicly available [HLS4ML jet dataset](#), we extract persistence images from Vietoris–Rips filtration of point clouds representing jet constituents. These persistence features are then fed into a convolution neural network (CNN) for binary jet tagging. The analysis demonstrates that persistent homology can efficiently capture geometric and structural distinctions among jets, achieving an AUC of 0.82 for quark–gluon classification.

Keywords: jet tagging, persistence homology, hep-ph, machine learning

1 Introduction

This study used the dataset from [HLS4ML](#) containing jet data of five categories: light quarks (q), gluons (g), W bosons, Z bosons, and top quarks (t). Particle jets formed after proton–proton collisions contain streams of particles that originate from a common vertex. In the rotated frame aligned to the jet axis, and taking into consideration the relativistic effect of transverse momentum, we take three coordinates for each constituent— p_T^{rel} , η_{rot} , and ϕ_{rot} . These features form a geometric structure that persistent homology can capture in the form of topological invariants. A convolution neural network (CNN) trained on these topological features classifies jets.

1.1 Dataset

We analyze the publicly available HLS4ML jet dataset [1], which contains jets originating from five categories: light quarks (q), gluons (g), W bosons, Z bosons, and top quarks (t). Each jet is represented as a set of up to 100 constituents and treating each constituent as a point in a point cloud (see Fig. 1).

(a) 100 Quarks jets.

(b) 100 Gluons jets.

Figure 1: Point cloud structures for quark and gluon jets from the HLS4ML dataset. Each jet is visualized in the three-dimensional feature space $(p_T^{rel}, \eta_{rot}, \phi_{rot})$, highlighting geometric differences between quark and gluon jets.

1.2 Jets and Coordinates

Jets are collimated cascades of particles produced at particle accelerators [2]. They form a funnel-like structure originating from their primary vertex. High-energy collisions often produce overlapping jets (see Fig. 2).. For each constituent, we use three observables: p_T^{rel} , η_{rot} , and ϕ_{rot} . Since persistent homology is invariant under global translations and rotations, using rotated coordinates does not affect topological results.

Figure 2: Structure of Jets.

2 Persistent Homology

Topological Data Analysis (TDA) aims to capture the shape of data across multiple scales or filtration parameters [3]. Persistent homology extracts features that persist across filtration, revealing intrinsic structures in data. The Betti-1 feature (the loop) persists between K_4 and K_5 (Fig. 3).

Figure 3: Filtration of a point cloud into a nested sequence of simplicial complexes, $K_1 \subseteq K_2 \subseteq \dots \subseteq K_5$. Reproduced from Dłotko, P. (2022). *Understanding Persistent Homology and Its Use in Data Analysis*. *PeerJ Computer Science*, 8:e1195, DOI: [10.7717/peerj-cs.1195](https://doi.org/10.7717/peerj-cs.1195), under a Creative Commons Attribution (CC BY 4.0) license.

3 Methods and Results

Jets are represented as point clouds, with each point corresponding to a jet constituent. For each jet, Vietoris–Rips filtration were computed with the ripser library to obtain H_0 (connected components) and H_1 (loops) persistence pairs. Figure 4 illustrates representative persistence diagrams for (connected components) and (loops), along with their corresponding persistence images.

To obtain a uniform numerical representation from these diagrams, we converted them into persistence images using the Persim package. Each persistence diagram was first rotated by 45 degrees to map coordinates from (birth, death) space to (birth, persistence) space, ensuring that the vertical axis represents the lifetime of topological features. The resulting persistence images were computed with a Gaussian kernel of bandwidth $\sigma = 0.001$, a resolution of 40×40 pixels, and birth/persistence ranges restricted to $[0, 0.20] \times [0, 0.20]$, capturing the most relevant topological scales in jet substructure. Each persistence image was normalized by its maximum intensity, flattened, and concatenated for H_0 and H_1 to form a fixed-size feature vector for supervised CNN training.

Figure 4: Persistence Images from Persistence Diagram.

We consider binary classification between quark–gluon jets. The CNN model demonstrates stable convergence during training and achieves strong discriminative performance between the two classes ($AUC = 0.82$) (Fig. 5a). The corresponding confusion matrix (Fig. 5b) shows that most jets are correctly identified, with a clear dominance along the diagonal entries, indicating reliable classification of quark and gluon jets.

Figure 5: CNN model training on Persistence Images.

4 Conclusion

The binary classification of quark and gluon jets demonstrates that persistence homology effectively captures the intrinsic topological structure of jet subcomponents. These rotation-invariant descriptors offer a robust representation that can enhance jet-tagging algorithms, while remaining computationally feasible for typical jet multiplicities.

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Code and Resources Availability

The complete source code, pre-processing scripts, and analysis notebooks used in this study are publicly available at:

https://github.com/Sauravi31/Topology_based_particle_Jet_tagging.

The dataset employed in this analysis is the open HLS4ML jet dataset [1], hosted on Zenodo under the CERN Open Data license.

References

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